

Urban Sprawl And Its Impacts On Environment – A Geographical Study Of Baghpat City

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Abstract Urban population is increasing day by day due to high birth rate and rural to urban migration. To fulfill the requirement of employment, transport, education, health, markets etc the urban area is sprawling and developing. Urban area is increasing and encouraging the agriculture land of rural area. Due to urbanization the area of green belt and natural vegetation is reducing. Due to reducing the chemical waste and polluted water the agriculture land is decreasing the fertility. Due to urbanization and industrialization the agriculture land has lost the quality and minerals which are essential for the crops and human. Water bodies has been reduced and underground water level also reduced due to urbanization. Many environmental problems are generated by the urbanization. Solid waste also created the environmental degradation problems here because there are poor management system is present here of the solid waste. Infrastructure development has changed the land use pattern and increased the urban area. The demand of facilities is increasing in the rural and urban areas. So the services are developing in urban areas to fulfill the requirement of the population. So the rate of urban development is increasing day by day.

Keywords Urbanization, Industrialization, Urban Sprawl, Environmental Degradation, Encroachment, Natural Vegetation.

Introduction

Urban sprawl is known as the spreading of the residential facilities, health facilities, educational facilities, employment facilities, transport facilities on undeveloped land near a more or less densely populated city. Urban sprawl is the result of population growth and encroachment of the rural area. Rural population is moving towards the city due to scarcity of the employment, education facilities, health facilities, markets facilities, security etc. So the development of the infrastructure is responsible to the urban sprawl. Urbanization and industrialization are also responsible to the urban growth. The sprawling nature of cities is critically important because of the major impacts that are evident in increased energy, land and soil consumption. Doe to develop the city on the rural land the problems of environmental degradation, noise pollution, water pollution, soil pollution, air pollution etc. are raised here. Due to increase the transportation facilities in the sprawled area of the city the level of the air pollution is increased. Using fossil fuels also results in the emission of other gases and particulates that degrade the air quality industries are shifting towards the rural areas, so the level of air pollution has increased in this areas.

Urban sprawl affected the soil quality. Its transformed the properties of soil, reducing its capacity to perform its essential functions. Due to increasing the numbers of the transport facilities the vehicles increased the problems of water quality due to run off the automobiles fuels, gas, metals etc. Its affected the treatments plants and decreased the quality of water. The price of the land has increased in rural urban fringe due to expansion of the area of the city. The pattern of the land use and land cover has been changed due to urban sprawl.

Objective of study

1. To analyse the changing of land use and land cover of the study area.
2. To analyse the changing of the population of the study area.
3. To analyse the causes of the urban sprawl of the study area.

Review of Literature

Many researcher has completed this research work on the research problem of urban sprawl and its impacts on environment. A review of literature is given here to analyse the research problem. Which is as- Baghel (2006) completed his research work on "Shikohabad, urban structure and interaction – A study of Shikohabad urban region." In this study they pointed that urban and rural areas have different types of functions. They analysed the interaction relation between the town and rural area. Urban area is increasing and adopting the rural land which is engaged in agriculture. Mauricio, Jose and Misian (2011) presented a research paper on "Environmental impacts of urban sprawl in Londrina, Parana, Brazil." They analysed that public policies encouraging the insertion of large industrial and commercial developments near highways, associated to exclusionary housing policies. They examined the impacts of urban sprawl on this city and analysed about the causes of green field reducing. They found that infrastructure is the main result of urban sprawl and environmental degradation. Priyanka Dubey and Dilip Kumar (2013) presented a research paper on "Urban sprawl and its impact on urban environment." They analysed that due to population growth the expansion of the urban area is increasing day by day and changing the land use pattern. They discussed about the urban sprawl of the Gorakhpur city through the land sat images. They used the G.I.S. and remote sensing methodology to analyse the changing of urban sprawl in different periods. Zuhail (2016) presented her research paper on "The concept of urban sprawl and its causes." She analysed that urban sprawl is a transition zones with indefinite borders between rural and urban areas. Socio-economic, technological and development policies etc. factors are responsible to the development of the urban areas. Natural resources are reducing and increasing the problems of environmental degradation. Urban sprawl damaged the eco-system. Industries, settlements, transport facilities and many activities are responsible to the urban sprawl and changed the land use pattern. Bhat, Shafiq, Mir and Ahmed (2016) presented a research paper on "Urban sprawl and its impact on land use/land cover dynamics of Dehradun city, India." They analysed about the rapid increases in both urban/built-up expansion led to dramatic changes in land use and land cover. They examined that last few years the study area has converted in urban areas. They find out that urban and built up area was 27.16 km² in 2004 and 34.08 km² in 2014. It has been changed 6.92 km² in the study area. Agriculture land was 25.45 km² in 2004 and 17.65 km² in 2014. It has been changed 7.50 km². It was covered by the urban sprawl. Rosni and Noor (2016) analysed the impacts and causes of the urban sprawl. In their study they analysed a temporal study during the period 1996 to 2015. They used bibliometric analyse techniques in their study. They attempted to examine the theoretical literature related to factors and causes of urban sprawl. Collins and Gbenekanur (2019) completed a research paper on "Urbanization and environmental impact of urban sprawl in Ogu Town, Rivers State, Nigeria." In this study they focused on urbanization and environmental degradation. They found that population explosion is the main causes of the urban sprawl. They analysed the impact of urban sprawl on environment. They observed that the rate of environmental and ecological distraction in this peri-urban town is alarming in the area as environmentally fragile land and shore lines including the mangroves forests and coastal wetlands are destroyed. Shao, Sumari, Portnor and Ujoh (2020) presented a paper on "Urban sprawl and its impact on sustainable urban development: A combination of remote sensing and social media data." They analysed that the built-up area of the Morogoro urban municipality expanded during the 2011 to 2017. They found that the agriculture land has decreased and eco-systems also changed in the study area. Chhanjani (2023) presented a research paper on "Comprehensive review in Indian context." They analysed that urban sprawl leads to the loss of agricultural land and increased infrastructure costs. Urban sprawl created economic disparities and environmental degradation. They suggested that sustainable development policies of the urban areas will be helpful to control the environmental problems. Urban sprawl puts immense pressure on natural resources. Loss of bio diversity, climate change, waste generation, increasing pollution level are another impacts of the urban sprawl on the environment.

Methodology

To complete the present study the researcher has used both types of data. Primary data has been collected by the personal interview method by using the schedule. Secondary data has been collected from the satellite image, district Baghpat statistical magazines and websites. On the basis of the images data the researcher has made an attempt to find the result about the urban sprawl and changing about the land use pattern.

Sampling

To complete the present study the researcher has selected 100 sample by randomly method of sampling. On the basis of the 100 sample the researcher has made an attempt to find out the result related to the research problem.

Result and Discussion

Research Problem

Population is increasing day by day and generating the problems of environmental degradation. Due to urbanization and industrialization the pattern of land use has been changed and degraded the environmental quality. Air, water and noise pollution is increasing in the urban area. Socio-economic and health facilities are establishing in urban area according to the population. Employment sources are developing in the urban area. To connect the rural area with the urban area the transportation facilities are establishing here rapidly. So the urban area is growing rapidly.

Study Area

To complete the present study the researcher has selected the Baghpat city. It is the headquarter of district Baghpat and situated at the bank of Yamuna river. Yamuna river created the natural boundary between Baghpat district and Haryana state. It is situated in western Uttar Pradesh and 45 km far from Delhi in northeast. It is 48 km west of Meerut. Baghpat district is bounded by Delhi, Meerut, Shamli, Muzaffarnagar and Ghaziabad.

Causes of Urban Sprawl in The Study Area

At present the population in urban areas is increasing day by day and the urban growth is very high due to urbanization and industrialization. Infrastructure development is going fast and physical structure is developed of the cities very fast after 2001. In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to find out the causes of urban sprawl in Baghpat city. Main causes of the urban sprawl in Baghpat city are given below–

Urbanization

Urbanization is a natural process which is responsible to urban sprawl. After 1991 the rate of urbanization is found very high in the study area. In 1991 the population of Baghpat city was 24939 and it has become 65000 in 2021. During in this period the growth of population is found 160.64% in this city. Population growth of Baghpat city is given below in the table–

Table-1

Urban Population Growth in Baghpat City (1991–2021)

Year	Population	Decadal Growth	Growth in %
1991	24939	–	–
2001	36384	11445	57.92
2011	50310	13926	38.28
2021	65000	14690	29.20

Source: Statistical Magazine of district Baghpat, Year 1999, 2007, 2015, 2023.

According to the above table the growth of urban population was 57.92% in 1991–2001 decade in Baghpat city. It was 38.28% in 2001–2011 and 29.20% in 2011–2021 in Baghpat city. During in 2011–2021 the annual growth of population is found 2.92%. It was 3.83% in 2001–2011 and 5.79% in 1991–2001. Population growth is responsible to the urban sprawl and is also responsible to the infrastructure development.

Industrialization–

Industries provide the employment and increase the physical area of the city. Due to fulfill the requirement of the population the industries are developing in the study area. After 1991 the industries are developed rapidly due to transportation development and the increasing of the demand of the products. Industrial development is given below in the table–

Table-2

Industrialization in the study area Baghpat City (2002–03 to 2022–23)

Year	Industries		
	Cottage Industries	Small Scale Industries	Medium Scale Industries
2002–03	05	20	06
2007–08	9	30	17
2012–13	9	30	22
2017–18	23	29	9

2022-23	43	18	13
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Source: Statistical Magazine of district Baghpat, Year 2003, 2008, 2013, 2018 and 2023.

According to the above table in the study area in 2002-03 there was present 05 cottage industries, 20 small scale industries and 06 medium scale industries in the study area. It has become cottage industries 43, small scale industries 18 and medium scale industries 13 in 2022-23 in the study area. The development of the industrial area is the result of industrial growth and increased the area of the city. Industrial development increased the infrastructure area and transportation facilities. These activities are responsible to the urban sprawl here.

Changing land use Pattern in Baghpat city

Changing land use pattern is the symbol of urban sprawl because the infrastructure development encroach the agriculture land urban area has not had own land. It is developed on the rural land. Agriculture land is converting into the residential area, industrial area and marketing area etc. So the urban sprawl is the result of changing land use pattern. Changing land use pattern of the Baghpat city is given below in the table-

Table-3

Changing land use pattern in Baghpat City (2006-2019)

S.No.	Land use	Area in Hectare		Changes
		2006	2019	
01	Forest Land	7.61	10.05	2.44
02	Agriculture Land	59.25	32.76	-26.49
03	Barren Land	56.34	34.56	-21.78
04	Aquatic Land	1.27	1.04	-0.23
05	Human Settlement Land	131.96	178.02	46.06
Total		256.43	256.43	00

Source: NRS.C Hyderabad, linear imaging self scanning sensor iv.

According to the above table the researcher has found that land use pattern has been changed in the study area during in this period 2006-2019. The forest land area was 7.61 hectare in 2006 in the study area and it was 10.05 hectare in 2019. During in this period it has been changed 2.44 hectare. Agriculture land was 59.25 hectare in 2006. It has become 32.76 hectare in 2019 in the study area. During in this period the agriculture land has been decreased 26.49 hectare in the study area. Barren land was 56.34 hectare in 2006 and it has become 34.56 hectare in 2019 in the study area. During in this period the barren land area has been reduced 21.78 hectare here aquatic land was 1.27 hectare and it has become 1.04 hectare in 2019 in the study area. During in this period it has been reduced 0.23 hectare in the study area. The settlement land was 131.96 hectare in 2006 and it has become 178.02 hectare in 2019 in the study area. During in this period the land of human settlement has been increased 46.06 hectare in the study area. On the basis of the above data we can say that land use pattern has been changed here during in this period. Due to reducing the agriculture land area and increasing the settlement area in the study area the urban sprawl is found here.

Development of Socio-Economic Facilities

The development of the socio-economic facilities is the result of urbanization. To fulfill the requirement of the population the facilities are established here educational, health, financial and transportation facilities etc. are essential to fulfill the requirement of the people. These facilities provide education, employment, treatment and financial support to fulfill the basic requirement. These facilities have covered a large space. So the area of the city has been increased. These facilities of the study area are given below-

Table-4

Development of Socio-Economic Facilities in the Study Area (2001-2023)

S.No.	Facilities	Units	Units	Changed
1.	Basic School	6	7	1
2.	Senior Basic School	4	4	0
3.	Intermediate College	1	1	0
4.	Optional Education Center	2	3	1
5.	College	1	1	0
6.	Allopathic Hospital	0	1	1
7.	Community Health Center	1	1	0
8.	Primary Health Center	1	1	0
9.	Nationalized Bank	4	6	2

10.	Non-Nationalized Bank	0	3	3
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Source: District Statistical Magazine, Baghpat District, Year 2001 and 2023

On the basis of the analysed of the above table we found that basic schools were 6 in 2001 in the study area Baghpat city in 2023 it has become 7 here. Senior basic schools are present here 4 and intermediate college is present here 1. Optional education center were 2 in 2001 and it has become 03 in 2023 here. There are present 1 college, 01 allopathic hospital, 01 community health center and 01 primary health center. There were present 04 nationalized banks in 2001 and they have become 6 in 2023 in the study area. Non-Nationalized banks are present here 03. Socio-economic facilities are developing in the study area and increased the constructed area. So the residential area is increasing and the services are developing here. So the Baghpat city area has been increased during in 2006–2019.

Impact of Urban Sprawl on Environment

Urban sprawl is the result of urbanization and industrialization. In the context of India the urban sprawl is characterized by the unplanned and uncontrolled expansion of cities, leading to the encroachment of agricultural land the depletion of the natural resources and the haphazard development of urban infrastructure. In the observation of the study area the infrastructure development towards the transportation facilities. The agriculture land is reducing and the human settlements area is increasing here. Some impacts are given here–

Impacts on Agriculture Land

Due to urbanization the agriculture land is reducing day by day. In 2006 the agriculture land was 59.25 hectare in Baghpat city and in 2019 it has become 32.76 hectare. During in this period the agriculture land has been reduced 26.49 hectare. Due to urbanization and industrialization it is reducing. It is the major impact of urban sprawl on environment and agriculture.

Changing in Human Settlements Area

In 2006 the settlements area was 131.96 hectare in Baghpat city. It was 150.56 hectare in 2012 and it has become 178.02 hectare in the study area. During in this period the settlements area has increased 46.06 hectare in the study area.

Impact on Forest Land

Forest land is reducing day by day due to urbanization and industrialization in 2006 the forest area was 7.61 hectare in Baghpat city and it was 1.95 hectare in 2012. During in this period the forest area has been reduced 5.66 hectare in the study area.

Air Pollution

In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to collect the primary data related to the air quality index. On the basis of the field survey we found the AQI level 235% very poor at Vandana Chowk, 47% at Collectrate, 126% at Sugar Mills, 147% at Kutchury 67% at Chandi Nagar, 74% at Yamuna Road, 90% at Municipality area and 158% at Gauripur Mod. In the present study we found that the air quality is reducing inside the city due to transportation activities and industrial activities.

Conclusion

Urbanization and industrialization are responsible to increase the area of city. Agriculture land is reducing rapidly due to socio-economic facilities development. The process of urban sprawl is going on in the study area. To fulfill the requirement of the residential area the colonies are developing here rapidly. To providing the employment the sources of employment are establishing here. Transportation facilities provided a platform to establish the socio-economic facilities to the people and urban sprawl. Health, Education, finance and social facilities are providing to the people for better future. Agriculture land is reducing and constructed area is increasing here. People are moving towards the city for the employment and health facilities. So the population growth is found high here. Due to reducing the green belt and agriculture land environmental degradation problems are increasing here.

Suggestions for the future 1. Urban sprawl is a natural process which is depend on the population growth and infrastructure development. Due to development of the infrastructure the agriculture land

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has reduced and the forest area has reduced rapidly. So many environmental problems are originated there and degrade the environment. So we need a future plan of the town development. Which should be related to the sustainable development.

2. To reduce the level of the pollution of the city we should control on the diesel and petrol vehicles and preference to the electric and CNG vehicles to running inside the city. To control the water pollution we need a solid waste management plan which will be helpful to control the environmental degradation problems.

3. The problem of environmental degradation is increasing day by day in the urban areas. Due to over population, poor management of solid waste, poverty and lack of resources. We need a plantation movement inside and outside of the city. We should planted of the trees on the road side and street side to control the air pollution.

4. Multi-story building plan should be prepare to control the encroachment of the agriculture land.

5. Water drainage system should be prepare on the basis of the requirement of the settlements to reduce the problems of water logging in rainy season. Water logging problem is generated many diseases inside the colony.

6. We need regularly cleaning the roads and streets to control the pollution and environmental degradation.

7. Industries should be established outside the city and residential area. Mostly industries generate solid waste which is creating the environmental problems.

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